

The kink drive in conventional high toroidal mode number ideal MHD for an axisymmetric toroidal configuration with a high fraction of bootstrap current

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Abstract. In this note we address the conventional high toroidal mode number, $n \gg 1$, ideal magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) for an axisymmetric tokamak geometry to find how kink drive enters the eigen value of the problem. We show that the σ'/n kink drive, where σ is the parallel current density normalised to equilibrium magnetic field and prime denotes its radial derivative, does not enter the eigen value when σ' remains finite. If σ' is large, e.g. due to high fraction of bootstrap current in tokamak pedestal, it is able to compete with $1/n$ in the kink drive term. This allows kink drive to be retained in the eigen value. A specific example is considered.

1. Introduction

In Sec.2 we solve the Euler-Lagrange problem with model pressure and current density profiles to find the eigen value when bootstrap current/kink drive is large. In Sec.3 we investigate the validity of the local ballooning theory and the corresponding integral transform for this case. In Appendix A we show that the σ'/n kink drive with $n \gg 1$ and finite σ' does not appear in the eigen value. More detailed derivations are presented in Appendix B and Appendix C.

2. $i \frac{\partial(\sigma' F_0)}{\partial y}$ in the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$ equation

Following the original paper [1], we introduce two length scales in the direction orthogonal to magnetic field: ψ is used for equilibrium quantities and $x = n^{1/2}(\psi - \psi_0)$ for rapidly varying perturbations, $n \gg 1$. ψ_0 is a stationary point of ω^2 [1]. The functional δW represents changes in potential energy and is given by Eq.(13) of [1] after minimising with respect to $Z(\xi_\varphi)$ and $U(\xi_\chi, \xi_\varphi)$, correct to $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$, written in terms of $X(\xi_\psi)$.^{1,2} The problem of its minimisation is equivalent to solving the Euler-Lagrange equation for $X = X(\psi, \chi/y)$ or $F = F(\psi, y)$:

$$(L + \Omega^2 M) F = 0.$$

¹ Here Z , U and X are known functions of ξ_φ , ξ_χ and ξ_ψ . The latter denotes the toroidal, poloidal and radial components of a plasma displacement vector, ξ , respectively.

² Here and below we use the same notations as in [1].

X and F are connected via Eqs.(16,17) of [1]. y here is a poloidal variable in ballooning space, i.e. conjugated to χ . It spans an infinite domain and thus releases the periodicity constraints. Ω is the eigen value of the problem. X is assumed to be radially localised and finite at infinity (as well as its x and y derivatives). The L and M operators are defined as in [1].

The $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ kink drive does not appear in the eigen value in [1]. This is the result of self-adjointness of the leading order operator (and not the localisation; self-adjointness of the leading order operator, in turn, might be the result of the local approach/eikonal ansatz), see Appendix A. This conventional kink drive decreases with n as $1/n$ and thus is considered as being negligible in the majority of problems. However, there are certain regions in a tokamak, where the kink drive is to be retained, e.g. a tokamak pedestal. There the density/temperature gradient is sufficiently steep to generate a strong bootstrap current and thus to provide a significant contribution to the current density gradient there. Therefore, σ' might compete with $1/n$ in a kink term in the last line of Eq.(13) of [1], which makes the kink drive appear in the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$ or even $\mathcal{O}(n^{-0})$ equation. The first case is considered below and is provided as an illustration to show that it is still possible for the kink drive to appear in the eigen value even in the conventional ideal MHD with the Hermitian leading order operator.

Following [1], for $\mathcal{O}(n^{-0})$ we write

$$[L_0 + \omega^2(\psi, y_0) M_0] F_0 = 0, \quad (1)$$

which is exactly Eq.(24) of [1]. Here $F_0 = F_0(x, y, \psi; y_0)$ and can be written as

$$F_0 = A(x) f_0(y, \psi; y_0) \quad (2)$$

since L_0 and M_0 act in y space only. A is any function of x and is to be determined later. Similar to the case where the kink drive appears in the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ equation, we have

$$|L_0 + \omega^2(\psi, y_0) M_0| f_0 = 0$$

and

$$\langle g | L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 | f_0 \rangle = \langle f_0 | L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 | g \rangle$$

for any g , i.e. the leading order operator is Hermitian. The $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$ equation reads

$$(L_0 + \omega^2 M_0) F_1 n^{-1/2} + (L_1 + \omega^2 M_1) F_0 n^{-1/2} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} (L_1 + \omega^2 M_1) F_0 n^{-1/2} &= (L_1^{org} + \omega^2 M_1) F_0 n^{-1/2} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\sigma' F_0) n^{-1} = \\ &= (\hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1) i \frac{dA}{dx} f_0 n^{-1/2} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\sigma' f_0) A n^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

L_1^{org} is L_1 in the previous notations of [1]. \hat{L}_1 , \hat{M}_1 and M_1 are defined as in the original paper. Here σ' should grow as $n^{1/2}$ to compensate $1/n$ and appear in $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$, i.e.

$$\sigma' \sim n^{1/2}.$$

To show that there is a solution for the eigen value for this case (at least, one) and to simplify the analysis below by working with an analytic form of a solution, we assume that

$$\frac{dA}{dx} = Cx A(x). \quad (4)$$

Roughly, this is based on the previously obtained form of A . If A is still Gaussian, C , which is unknown at this stage, will be an argument of the exponent.³ σ' contains fast, $\sim n^{1/2}(\psi - \psi_0)$ variation, and thus is to be written as a function of x . Here ψ_0 is taken close to the position of a pedestal. Considering a narrow pedestal region of a plasma with a steep pressure gradient, we introduce

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma' &= \frac{Ip''}{B^2} \left[1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (1 - L_{bs}) \right] = \\ &= -\frac{I}{B^2} \frac{2}{\delta^2} ap_0(\psi) \operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\psi - \psi_0}{\delta}\right) \operatorname{th}\left(\frac{\psi - \psi_0}{\delta}\right) \left[1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (1 - L_{bs}) \right] = \\ &= -\frac{I}{B^2} \frac{2}{\delta^3} ap_0(\psi) \frac{x}{n^{1/2}} \left[1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (1 - L_{bs}) \right] + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\psi - \psi_0}{\delta}\right)^3,\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

Taylor expanded around $\psi = \psi_0$ (to simplify the below derivations). This model is explained in Appendix B. Here $I = RB_\varphi$ is the poloidal current with R being the major radius and B_φ the toroidal component of magnetic field, B . p is the plasma pressure, being the flux surface quantity enumerated by ψ . a is a dimensionless constant, and p_0 is a function that varies on equilibrium length scale, ψ . δ is a width of the pedestal and $\delta \ll \psi_0$. L_{bs} is a dimensionless function of trapped particle fraction, collisionality and a ratio of density to temperature length scales. A prime denotes the derivative with respect to ψ , and angular brackets represent a flux surface average. This expression is correct if the ψ dependence in p'' is stronger than in L_{bs} . Then Eq.3 becomes

$$(L_0 + \omega^2 M_0) F_1 + \left(\hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right) f_0 i \frac{dA}{dx} - 2i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\hat{L}_{bs} f_0 \right) I p_0(\psi) \frac{x}{n} A = 0 \quad (6)$$

with

$$\hat{L}_{bs} = \frac{a}{B^2 \delta^3} \left[1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (1 - L_{bs}) \right]. \quad (7)$$

Using the above assumption for dA/dx , dividing both sides of Eq.6 by $ixA(x)$ and defining

$$f_1 = \frac{F_1}{ixA(x)},$$

we obtain

$$(L_0 + \omega^2 M_0) f_1 + \left(\hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right) f_0 C - 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\hat{L}_{bs} f_0 \right) \frac{I p_0(\psi)}{n} = 0, \quad (8)$$

similar to the situation when the kink drive appears to $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ in δW (and then is eliminated from Ω as shown in Appendix A). Here all operators act in y space, and the ψ and y_0 dependencies are parametric. Multiplying both sides of Eq.8 by f_0 and integrating over y , we obtain

$$\left\langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right| f_0 \right\rangle = \frac{2}{C} \left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{L}_{bs} \right| f_0 \right\rangle \frac{I p_0}{n}, \quad (9)$$

where the first term of Eq.8 is annihilated since the leading order operator is still Hermitian and Eq.1 is still valid.^{4,5} Eq.9 now replaces Eq.(29) of [1].

³ This assumption is not necessary, however, is useful to obtain an analytic form of a solution.

⁴ C is independent of x and y , but might be a function of ψ and y_0 .

⁵ Here $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{L}_{bs} \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\hat{L}_{bs} \cdot)$

Differentiating Eq.3 with respect to y_0 and then using Eq.(22) of [1] with Eq.9, we find

$$\frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} = \frac{2}{C} \frac{\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{L}_{bs} \right| f_0 \rangle}{\langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle} \frac{I p_0}{n} \nu'(y_0). \quad (10)$$

In the absence of the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$ kink drive, this reduces to Eq.(30) of [1]. We note that $f_{0,1} = f_{0,1}(y)$ are known at this stage as solutions of Eq.1 and Eq.8, respectively. An explicit equation for $f_1 = f_1(y)$ can be obtained if the x dependence is eliminated from the equation. This, in turn, explains the origin of the assumption we made about dA/dx above. We also note that $\partial \omega^2 / \partial y_0$ does not contain any rapid radial variations since $1/\delta^3$ in \hat{L}_{bs} compensates $1/n$. The latter will be addressed in the following section.

Proceeding to next order, we write for the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ operator

$$\begin{aligned} & - \langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_2 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_2 \right| f_0 \rangle \frac{d^2 A}{dx^2} + \langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \rangle A + \\ & - \langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right| f_1 \rangle \frac{d(xA)}{dx} + \langle f_0 \left| i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \sigma' \right| f_1 \rangle i x A + \langle f_0 \left| L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 \right| F_2 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

since

$$L_2 = -\hat{L}_2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \tilde{L}_2 = -\hat{L}_2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \tilde{L}_2^{org} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\sigma' \cdot),$$

where \tilde{L}_2^{org} denotes the original \hat{L}_2 operator introduced in [1], and \hat{L}_2 now denotes one that excludes the kink drive. The last term in the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ operator is annihilated since the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-0})$ operator is Hermitian and Eq.1. Here the kink drive operator is $i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \sigma' \equiv i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\sigma' \cdot)$. It can be shown that

$$\langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right| f_1 \rangle = \frac{1}{\nu'(y_0)} \left\langle \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y_0} \left| L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 \right| f_1 \right\rangle + \frac{1}{\nu'(y_0)} \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_1 \rangle \quad (11)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_2 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_2 \right| f_0 \rangle = \\ & = -\frac{1}{(\nu'(y_0))^2} \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} \left[\left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial y_0} \right| f_0 \right\rangle - \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{2\nu'(y_0)} \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_0 \rangle \right] - \frac{1}{2(\nu'(y_0))^2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_0 \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Substituting these into the above expression for the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ operator and adding the Ω dependent part, we obtain the following equation to be solved for $A = A(x)$:

$$a \frac{d^2 A}{dx^2} + b A + c \left(x \frac{dA}{dx} + A \right) + c_2 x^2 A + \left[n (\Omega^2 - \omega^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial \psi^2} x^2 \right] \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_0 \rangle A = 0, \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \frac{1}{(\nu'(y_0))^2} \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} \left[\left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial y_0} \right| f_0 \right\rangle - \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{2\nu'(y_0)} \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_0 \rangle \right] + \frac{1}{2(\nu'(y_0))^2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_0 \rangle, \\ b &= \langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \rangle, \\ c &= -\frac{1}{\nu'(y_0)} \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_1 \rangle - \frac{1}{\nu'(y_0)} \left\langle f_1 \left| L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 \right| \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y_0} \right\rangle, \\ c_1 &= \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial \psi^2}, \quad c_2 = - \left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \sigma' \right| f_1 \right\rangle = 2 \left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{L}_{bs} \right| f_1 \right\rangle \frac{I p_0}{n^{1/2}} \\ d &= \langle f_0 \left| M_0 \right| f_0 \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The solution of Eqs.13,4 can be written through a linear combination of parabolic cylinder functions [2], where one branch is infinite at $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$ and thus is to be omitted. The first three solutions of the finite branch as a function of x are shown in Fig.1. Since the solution is required to be localised radially around $\psi = \psi_0$, we set the first argument of the solution to zero, which corresponds to the Gaussian form of A as a function of x and provides

$$\Omega^2 = \omega_0^2 - \frac{2b + c - \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d}}{2dn}. \quad (15)$$

C implicitly appears in Eq.15 through $\partial^2\omega^2/\partial y_0^2$. Its calculation requires $A = A(x)$ to be

Figure 1. The parabolic cylinder function, D_n , vs. x for $n = 0, 1, 2$. The number of local extrema is $n + 1$.

re-expressed in terms of the confluent hypergeometric function/Hermite polynomials and is discussed in Appendix C in detail. The kink drive appears through c_2 and partially through $\partial\omega^2/\partial y_0$ in a and c . Terms $\langle f_0 | \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial y_0} | f_0 \rangle$, $\langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle$, $\langle f_0 | \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 | f_0 \rangle$, $\langle f_0 | M_0 | f_1 \rangle$, $\langle f_1 | L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 | \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y_0} \rangle$ and $\langle f_0 | \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{L}_{bs} | f_1 \rangle$ are known and are independent of x and y being functions of ψ and y_0 only.

To summarise, the following key assumptions have been made:

- $dA/dx = CxA$,
- σ' has been introduced as a function of x since it has rapid radial variation in the vicinity of the pedestal. It has then been Taylor expanded around ψ_0 .
- ψ_0 has been chosen close to the location of the pedestal.

3. Validity of local ballooning theory for large kink drive

For validity of a local ballooning theory, we have to provide a separation of length scales: the equilibrium length scale, a scale of a tokamak minor radius, is the longest; an intermediate length

scale connected to the radial extent of the mode ($\sim n^{1/2}$ rational surfaces) and the smallest length scale associated with the distance between rational surfaces. The second condition to be maintained is a relatively slow variation of equilibrium profiles across rational surfaces. On the other hand, in the pedestal we have a rapid radial variation in σ' or p'' . Therefore, to ensure their slow variation from one rational surface to another one, we require a large number of rational surfaces across the pedestal region.

The poloidal variables, ϑ and χ , are connected via

$$\vartheta q = \int^x \nu d\chi,$$

where q is the safety factor, so that

$$\vartheta q' = \int^x \nu' d\chi$$

if $\vartheta' = 0$ in the absence of the Shafranov shift.⁶ To keep length scales separated, we have to ensure that

$$\frac{c + \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d}}{4a} = -\frac{C}{2} \sim 1$$

in A , where C has been introduced in the previous section and determined in Appendix C. Its explicit form is given by Eq.C.3 of Appendix C. Roughly, from Eq.5 (here and below dimensional parameters that do not change the order will be omitted)

$$\sigma' \sim \frac{x}{\delta^3 n^{1/2}}$$

and

$$c_2 \sim \frac{1}{\delta^3 n^{1/2}}.$$

Since all three terms in C in Eq.C.3 are of the same size,⁷ C is negative and

$$0 > C \sim -\frac{b}{3a} = -\frac{(2a_1 + c'')}{3a_2} = -\frac{4}{3} \frac{\frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0} \left[\left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial y_0} \right| f_0 \right\rangle - \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{2\nu'(y_0)} \langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle \right]}{\frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle} +$$

$$+ \frac{2\nu' \left\langle f_1 \left| L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 \right| \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y_0} \right\rangle}{3 \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle},$$

From Eq.10,

$$\frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} = \frac{1}{C} \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0},$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0} \sim \frac{1}{1 + \left(\int^y \nu' dy \right)^2} \frac{1}{\delta^3 n^{1/2}} \frac{\nu'(y_0)}{n^{1/2}}.$$

⁶ If y_0 from Eq.10 corresponds to the X point where the poloidal component of magnetic field, $B_\vartheta = 0$, then $\vartheta q' \approx \nu'(y_0)$.

⁷ This can be easily checked once a , b , c and d of Appendix C are written in terms of Eq.C.4.

$$\begin{aligned}
\textcircled{1} &\sim \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0} \frac{\langle f_0 | \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial y_0} | f_0 \rangle}{\langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \right)^{-1} \sim - \frac{2 \int^y \nu' dy}{\left[1 + \left(\int^y \nu' dy \right)^2 \right]^2} \frac{1}{\delta^3 n^{1/2}} \frac{(\nu'(y_0))^2}{n^{1/2}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \right)^{-1}, \\
\textcircled{2} &\sim \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0} \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{2\nu'(y_0)} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \right)^{-1} \sim \frac{1}{1 + \left(\int^y \nu' dy \right)^2} \frac{1}{\delta^3 n^{1/2}} \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{n^{1/2}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \right)^{-1}, \\
\textcircled{3} &\sim \nu'(y_0) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \right)^{-1}.
\end{aligned}$$

Since all terms are of the same sign, we require

$$\textcircled{1} \sim \textcircled{2} \sim \textcircled{3} \sim 1$$

and thus $\textcircled{1} \sim \textcircled{2}$ gives

$$\frac{q'}{1 + (q')^2} \sim \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{(\nu'(y_0))^2}$$

and $\textcircled{2} \sim \textcircled{3}$ gives

$$1 + (q')^2 \sim \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{\delta^3 n \nu'(y_0)}.$$

Hence,

$$q' \sim \frac{(\nu''(y_0))^2}{(\nu'(y_0))^3} \frac{1}{\delta^3 n}. \quad (16)$$

If ν' and ν'' evaluated at y_0 are of order one, then

$$q' \delta^3 n \sim 1. \quad (17)$$

As $\sigma' \sim \frac{x}{\delta^3 n^{1/2}} \sim n^{1/2}$,

$$\psi - \psi_0 \sim \delta^3 n^{1/2}$$

On the other hand, the Taylor expansion of σ' in the vicinity of ψ_0 is valid if

$$\psi - \psi_0 \ll \delta$$

and thus

$$\delta \ll n^{-1/4}, \quad \delta^3 n^{1/2} \ll \delta.$$

Multiplying both sides of this by $q' n^{1/2}$ and using Eq.17, we find

$$1 \ll \delta q' N, \quad (18)$$

where $N \sim n^{1/2}$. If y_0 corresponds to the X point so that ν' and ν'' are strongly growing, e.g. $\nu'' \sim (\nu')^2$ and $\nu' \sim n^{1/2}$, Eq.16 gives

$$q' \delta^3 n^{3/2} \sim 1$$

and

$$1 \ll \delta q' n.$$

Therefore, we can introduce fast variation compared to equilibrium quantities and maintain slow variation while jumping from one rational surface to another one.

4. Summary and conclusions

We have considered a specific example when kink drive is large and is retained in the eigen value and discussed the validity of the local ballooning transform for this case.

Appendix A. Kink drive in conventional ideal MHD, based on [1]

In the case described in [1], the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-0})$ equation is identical to that considered in Sec.2. The leading order operator is self-adjoint. The $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$ equation reads

$$(L_0 + \omega^2 M_0) F_1 + (L_1 + \omega^2 M_1) F_0 = 0. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

After dividing its both sides by idA/dx and making use of the fact that the leading order operator acts in y space only, Eq.A.1 can be rewritten as

$$(L_0 + \omega^2 M_0) f_1 + (\hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1) f_0 = 0$$

with

$$f_1 = \frac{F_1}{idA/dx}.$$

To eliminate the first term, we multiply both sides by f_0 and integrate over y to find

$$\langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 | f_0 \rangle = 0. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Here we have used self-adjointness of the leading order operator and Eq.1. In Sec.2 the later equation is not homogeneous due to the presence of kink drive in $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$. Eq.A.2 provides

$$\frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} = 0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

in comparison to Eq.10.

The last contribution from Eq.(15) of [1] is provided by terms of order $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$. Taylor expanding ω^2 around ψ_0 , the stationary point of ω^2 , we write

$$\omega^2 = \omega_0^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial \psi^2} \frac{x^2}{n} + \mathcal{O}(\psi - \psi_0)^3,$$

where functions of ψ are assumed to be evaluated in the vicinity of ψ_0 . The $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ operator reads

$$\langle f_0 | L_2 + \omega^2 M_2 | F_0 \rangle + \langle f_0 | L_1 + \omega^2 M_1 | F_1 \rangle + \langle f_0 | L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 | F_2 \rangle =$$

which can be rewritten as

$$= - \left\langle f_0 \left| \left(\hat{L}_2 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_2 \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right| F_0 \right\rangle + \left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle A + \langle f_0 | L_1 + \omega^2 M_1 | F_1 \rangle$$

using Eq.(22) of [1]. The F_2 term here vanishes since the leading order operator is Hermitian and Eq.1. The second term contains kink drive in \tilde{L}_2 and can be written as (this expression is to be checked later in this section)

$$\left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle = \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \psi} \left\langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right| f_0 \right\rangle - \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial \psi} \left\langle f_0 \left| \hat{M}_1 \right| f_0 \right\rangle. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Here the first term on the right hand side is zero due to Eq.A.2 from $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1/2})$ (and thus is the result of self-adjointness of the leading order operator), and the second term vanishes as $\partial\omega^2/\partial\psi$ is to be evaluated at the stationary point of ω^2 , ψ_0 , i.e.

$$\left. \frac{\partial\omega^2}{\partial\psi} \right|_{\psi_0} = 0,$$

the solution is localised around ψ_0 . Thus, the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ operator becomes

$$= - \left\langle f_0 \left| \left(\hat{L}_2 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_2 \right) \right| f_0 \right\rangle \frac{d^2 A}{dx^2} + \left\langle f_0 \left| L_1 + \omega^2 M_1 \right| F_1 \right\rangle. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Here $\left\langle f_0 \left| \left(\hat{L}_2 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_2 \right) \right| f_0 \right\rangle$ and $\left\langle f_0 \left| L_1 + \omega^2 M_1 \right| F_1 \right\rangle$ can be simplified using Eqs.11,12 with Eq.A.3. Substituting this into Eq.A.5 and then into the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ equation, Eq.(31) of [1], multiplied by f_0 and integrated over y , we obtain an equation for $A = A(x)$. The radial localisation requirement provides the constraint for the eigen value of the problem, Ω (similar to Sec.2). In this case Ω does not contain kink drive as \tilde{L}_2 satisfies

$$\left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle = \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left\langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_1 \right| f_0 \right\rangle \quad (\text{A.6})$$

and has been eliminated by Eq.A.2 and thus by self-adjointness of the leading order operator.

Appendix A.1. Proof of

$$\left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle = \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left\langle f_0 \left| \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 \right| f_0 \right\rangle - \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial\omega^2}{\partial\psi} \left\langle f_0 \left| \hat{M}_1 \right| f_0 \right\rangle$$

A contribution to $\left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle$ from

$$\begin{aligned} & i \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial(\sigma' f_0)}{\partial y} dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \sigma f_0 \frac{\partial \hat{Q} f_0}{\partial y} dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{p'}{B^2} f_0 \frac{\partial \hat{P} f_0}{\partial y} dy + \\ & + i \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{I B_{\chi}^2}{\nu B^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial \hat{Q} f_0}{\partial y} \right] dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{I^2}{\nu R^2 B^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial \hat{P} f_0}{\partial y} \right] dy = \end{aligned}$$

reduces to

$$= i \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial(\sigma' f_0)}{\partial y} dy$$

due to the integration by parts (\hat{P} and \hat{Q} are given on p.17 of [1]). Here we have assumed f_0 being finite at infinity and used the fact that I and the total plasma pressure are flux surface quantities, $p = p(\psi)$, $dp/d\psi \equiv p'$ (similar for I). Therefore, $\left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\langle f_0 \left| \tilde{L}_2 + \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 \right| f_0 \right\rangle = \\ & = i \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{R^2 B_{\chi}^2}{J B^2} \int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} \right] dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \sigma' f_0 \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} dy + \\ & + 2i \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{R^2 B_{\chi}^2}{J B^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial^2 f_0}{\partial\psi \partial y} \right] dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{I p'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} f_0 \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial\psi} dy + \\ & + i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \omega^2 f_0^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left[\frac{J R^2 B_{\chi}^2}{B^2} \int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right] dy + 2i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \omega^2 f_0 \frac{J R^2 B_{\chi}^2}{B^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial\psi} dy, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where \tilde{M}_2 is given by a sum of the second and third terms in Eq.(B6) of [1]. On the other hand, let us consider $\frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 | f_0 \rangle$, where \hat{L}_1 and \hat{M}_1 are given by Eqs.(B3, B4) with Eq.(21) of [1]. Differentiating $\langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 | f_0 \rangle$ with respect to ψ , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 | f_0 \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial\psi} \left\{ 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{R^2 B_\chi^2}{JB^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} \right] - \frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} f_0 \right\} dy + \\ &+ \int_{\mathbb{R}} dy f_0 \left\{ 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{R^2 B_\chi^2}{JB^2} \int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} \right] + 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{R^2 B_\chi^2}{JB^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial^2 f_0}{\partial\psi \partial y} \right] - \right. \\ &\left. - \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} \right) f_0 - \frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial\psi} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since (we assume f_0 satisfies Schwartz's theorem)

$$\begin{aligned} &2 \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial\psi} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{R^2 B_\chi^2}{JB^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} \right] dy + 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{R^2 B_\chi^2}{JB^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial^2 f_0}{\partial\psi \partial y} \right] dy = \\ &= 4 \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{R^2 B_\chi^2}{JB^2} \left(\int_{y_0}^y \nu' dy \right) \frac{\partial^2 f_0}{\partial\psi \partial y} \right] dy, \end{aligned}$$

we obtain

$$\langle f_0 | \tilde{L}_2 | f_0 \rangle = \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 | f_0 \rangle + \frac{i}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} \right) f_0^2 dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \sigma' f_0 \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} dy. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The last two terms of Eq.A.8 cancel out. Indeed,

$$\frac{i}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} \right) f_0^2 dy - i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \sigma' f_0 \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y} dy = \frac{i}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} \right) f_0^2 dy + \frac{i}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_0^2 \frac{\partial \sigma'}{\partial y} dy. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Comparing integrands in Eq.A.9, we find

$$\frac{\partial \sigma'}{\partial y} = - \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \left(\frac{Ip'}{B^4} \frac{\partial B^2}{\partial y} \right),$$

provided $I = I(\psi)$, and hence Eq.A.6, where the kink term appears through σ' in \tilde{L}_2 or, which is equivalent, through $\partial \hat{L}_1 / \partial \psi$.

Similarly, we check the following

$$\langle f_0 | \omega^2 \tilde{M}_2 | f_0 \rangle = \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 | f_0 \rangle - \frac{i}{2} \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \hat{M}_1 | f_0 \rangle. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Summing Eq.A.6 and Eq.A.10 leads to Eq.A.4. At this stage a part of kink drive is in $\langle f_0 | \tilde{L}_2 | f_0 \rangle$ and thus in $\frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 | f_0 \rangle$, but since

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial\psi} \langle f_0 | \hat{L}_1 + \omega^2 \hat{M}_1 | f_0 \rangle = 0$$

(consequence of the fact that the leading order operator is Hermitian), kink drive does not appear in Ω . *The fact that the $\mathcal{O}(n^{-1})$ kink drive does not appear in Ω in ideal MHD is the result of self-adjointness of the leading order operator (and not the localisation; self-adjointness of the leading order operator might be the result of the local approach).*

Appendix B. The parallel current density model in the pedestal

We consider a narrow pedestal region which is characterised by a strong pressure (density/temperature) gradient and hence strong gradients in bootstrap current. There the main contribution to the current is constructed from the diamagnetic, Pfirsch-Shluter and bootstrap current. The latter flows along the magnetic field lines and has zero divergence. The diamagnetic current associated with the plasma pressure gradient is not divergence free and thus is balanced by the Pfirsch-Shluter current parallel to the field lines. Defining the normalised parallel current density as $\sigma = j_{\parallel}/B$, we have

$$\sigma = I' + \frac{Ip'}{B^2}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The rest is defined as in Eq.5. σ is then constructed as a sum of the Pfirsch-Shluter current

$$\mathbf{j}_{ps} = \frac{Ip'}{B^2} \left(1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} \right) \mathbf{B} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

and bootstrap current

$$\mathbf{j}_{bs} = \frac{Ip' L_{bs}}{\langle B^2 \rangle} \mathbf{B}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

provided by the neoclassical theory. Rearranging Eqs.B.1,B.2 and B.3, we find

$$I' = \frac{Ip'}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (L_{bs} - 1)$$

and hence

$$\sigma = \frac{Ip'}{B^2} \left[1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (1 - L_{bs}) \right].$$

Kink modes are driven by a current density gradient. In the tokamak pedestal, the dominant contribution to the current density gradient is provided by p' , and thus we have

$$\sigma' = \frac{Ip''}{B^2} \left[1 - \frac{B^2}{\langle B^2 \rangle} (1 - L_{bs}) \right].$$

Note that L_{bs} being a function of ratio of density to temperature gradient length scales might also contain large density/temperature radial derivatives if the corresponding distributions are not aligned; this is neglected now. In Eq.5 we adopt a model pressure profile of the form:

$$p(\psi) = p_0(\psi) \left[1 + a \text{th} \left(\frac{\psi - \psi_0}{\delta} \right) \right].$$

p_0 is considered as a slowly varying function of ψ . We consider $\delta \ll \psi_0$, so that th (th denotes the hyperbolic tangent) describes a transport barrier of a width δ , centered about $\psi = \psi_0$. This once substituted into the above expression for σ' gives Eq.5.

Appendix C. Calculation of C

Solving Eq.13 with three extra constraints:

- Eq.4,
- $A|_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} \rightarrow 0$,
- the radial localisation requirement,

for A as a function of x , we find

$$\begin{aligned}
 A = & C_1 e^{-\frac{(c + \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d})}{4a} x^2} H_{\frac{2b+c - \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d} + 2dn(-\omega^2 + \Omega^2)}{2\sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d}}} \left(\frac{(c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d)^{1/4} x}{\sqrt{2a}} \right) + \\
 & + C_2 e^{-\frac{(c + \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d})}{4a} x^2} \times \\
 & \times {}_1F_1 \left(-\frac{2b+c - \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d} + 2dn(-\omega^2 + \Omega^2)}{4\sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d}}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d} x^2}{2a} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.1}$$

with Eq.15, which is equivalent to D_0 shown in Fig.1. Here H is used for the Hermite polynomials and ${}_1F_1$ for the confluent hypergeometric function; $C_{1,2}$ are arbitrary constants. To ensure Eq.4, we write

$$C = -\frac{c + \sqrt{c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d}}{2a} \tag{C.2}$$

for both branches in Eq.C.1. In Eq.C.2, a and c are functions of C through Eq.10. Substituting Eq.10 into a and c and then into Eq.C.2, we obtain a cubic equation to be solved for C (two complex solutions are to be dropped):

$$4a_2^2 C^3 + 4(2a_1 + c'') a_2 C^2 + 4 \left(a_1^2 + a_1 c'' + a_2 c' + a_2 c_2 - \frac{a_2 c_1 d}{2} \right) C + 4a_1 \left(c' + c_2 - \frac{c_1 d}{2} \right) = 0, \tag{C.3}$$

where we have defined

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \omega^2}{\partial y_0} &= \frac{1}{C} \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0}, \\
 a_1 &= \frac{1}{(\nu'(y_0))^2} \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0} \left[\left\langle f_0 \left| \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial y_0} \right| f_0 \right\rangle - \frac{\nu''(y_0)}{2\nu'(y_0)} \langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle \right] \\
 a_2 &= \frac{1}{2(\nu'(y_0))^2} \frac{\partial^2 \omega^2}{\partial y_0^2} \langle f_0 | M_0 | f_0 \rangle, \\
 c' &= -\frac{1}{\nu'(y_0)} \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}^2}{\partial y_0} \langle f_0 | M_0 | f_1 \rangle, \quad c'' = -\frac{1}{\nu'(y_0)} \left\langle f_1 \left| L_0 + \omega^2 M_0 \right| \frac{\partial f_0}{\partial y_0} \right\rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.4}$$

so that

$$a = \frac{a_1}{C} + a_2, \quad c = \frac{c'}{C} + c''.$$

Here $\partial\omega^2/\partial y_0$, a_1 , a_2 , c' and c'' as well as c_1 , c_2 and d are independent of C , x and y and are functions of y_0 and ψ . Solving the above cubic equation, we obtain an analytic expression for C in terms of a_1 , a_2 , c' , c'' , c_1 , c_2 , d :

$$C = -\frac{b}{3a} - \frac{2^{1/3} (3ac - b^2)}{3a \left(-2b^3 + 9abc - 27a^2d + \sqrt{4(3ac - b^2)^3 + (-2b^3 + 9abc - 27a^2d)^2} \right)^{1/3}} + \frac{\left(-2b^3 + 9abc - 27a^2d + \sqrt{4(3ac - b^2)^3 + (-2b^3 + 9abc - 27a^2d)^2} \right)^{1/3}}{3 \times 2^{1/3}a}, \quad (\text{C.5})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 4a_2^2, \\ b &= 4(2a_1 + c'')a_2, \\ c &= 4 \left(a_1^2 + a_1c'' + a_2c' + a_2c_2 - \frac{a_2c_1d}{2} \right), \\ d &= 4a_1 \left(c' + c_2 - \frac{c_1d}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

are to be expressed in terms of Eq.C.4. Then substituting C into Eq.10 provides $\partial\omega^2/\partial y_0$. Similar to [1], we do not express $\partial^2\omega^2/\partial y_0^2$ via $\partial\omega^2/\partial y_0$. Once C and $\partial\omega^2/\partial y_0$ are known, we find Ω from Eq.15. Then it can be easily estimated that $c^2 - 4ac_2 + 2ac_1d$ is not negative and thus $\Omega^2 \in \mathbb{R}$.

References

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